

Peculiar use of set expressions in English and Karakalpak languages

Kaipanova Fatima Ganibaevna

Master student of Karakalpak State University

Abstract

The main purpose of this article is to consider the study of Phraseological units, phraseological word combinations, set expressions, set phrases and their using approaches in English and Karakalpak languages. Linguistic features of set expressions, phraseological units, lingua-cultural aspects of target languages, the functional semantic classification of phraseological word combinations expressing their different relationships.

Key words: Phraseological units, set expressions, set phrases, word-equivalents, idiomatic word groups.

Introduction

Phraseological units, set phrases, word-equivalents, set expressions, idiomatic word groups all linguistic disciplines have defined according to their semantic, stylistic, lexicological features by different scientists. In human life, they have used in communication process, especially spoken language and also written form. In linguistic point of view, these disciplines traditionally defined that they are ready-made units which means they are not created during the communication process, language users organized their speech with their using forms. In addition to this, they also belong to communicators' intentions, cultural and natural aspects, background knowledge, and personal experience during their process of communication. The use of phraseological units, or set phrases, set expressions are mainly created their linguistic features depending on phraseological context. In phraseology have great important substances about all disciplines.

In linguistics, phraseology is the study of set or fixed expressions, such as

idioms, phrasal verbs, and other types of multiword lexical units (often collectively referred to as phrasemes), in which the component parts of the expression take on a meaning more specific than, or otherwise not predictable from, the sum of their meanings when used independently.[1]

Multi-word groups learned by intentional course of linguistics which specifically searched and made important results in phraseology. The British lexicographer and researcher Cowie pointed that have a great meaning and importance of phraseology in Western Linguistics for the past twenty years. He said that the role of Eastern European, especially, Russian Linguistic tradition in growth. Learning and searching conditions found that many scientists used different terms under the general and specific categories about phraseological phenomena. For instance, Linguists A.V.Kunin and I.V.Arnold prefer to “set expressions”, V.V. Vinogradov and Gläser’s term is “phraseological units”, L.Minaeva used “Multi –word units”.

Material and Methods.

This research found peculiarities of use of set expressions in English and Karakalpak languages. Communication process more important in human being which means that words and word groups, sentences to organise human attentions, their intentions, and life styles. This process have lead to our aims when we use it in true conditions. In linguistic features of sentences defined with generally and complex way. Word groups, set phrases, set expressions have their essence in many scientists works in both languages.

With the general category (umbrella term) ‘set expression’, which emphasizes the criteria of phraseological stability and setness of such units, and is more comprehensive (including sentence-like units too), the linguist proposes the following groups: phraseological units, phraseomatic units and the mixed class of borderline cases.[2, p 168].

According to Kunin, phraseological units have fully or partially transferred meanings:

- <i>red tape,</i>
- <i>a mare's nest</i>
- <i>grind one's teeth</i>
- <i>small hours</i>

while the members of phraseomatic units are used in their literal meanings:

- <i>win a victory</i>
- <i>launch a campaign</i>
- <i>cause/ make/ create a stir</i>
- <i>make/ achieve progress/ headway</i>
- <i>ask/ look for trouble</i>

[3, p 168]

Set expressions and it's classification mentioned A.V.Kunin's work. According to phraseological stability, stability of use, lexical-semantic stability set expressions can be defined: (Figure 1.1)

Set expressions		
Phraseological Units:	Phraseomatic Units	Mixed Class
- <i>Red tape</i>	- <i>Win a victory</i>	
- <i>Mare's nest</i>	- <i>Launch a company</i>	

- <i>Show one's teeth</i>		
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(Figure 1.1)

Another linguist R.Gläser emphasized that characteristics of lexicalization, stability of use, semantic and syntactic stability, idiomaticity, expressive functions in the text about linguistic phenomena.

“Gläser defines a ‘phraseological unit’ (her umbrella term) as a lexicalized, reproducible billexemic or polylexemic word group in common use, which has relative syntactic and semantic stability, may be idiomatized, may carry connotations, and may have an emphatic or intensifying function in a text”. [4, p 169].Gläser's approach conduct about idioms and non-idioms, technical terms, onymic entities, clichés etc. Propositions in Gläser's system are represented by

- **proverbs** (*One swallow does not make a summer*),
- **commonplaces/ trite formulae** (*We live and learn*),
- **routine formulae** (*Come again? Many happy returns*),
- **slogans** (*Value for money; Safety first*),
- **commandments and maxims** (*Thou shalt not kill; Be relevant!*),
- **quotations and winged words** (*Where ignorance is bliss, 'tis folly to be wise; A Jekyll and Hyde; Catch 22*).

R. Gläser's classification: (Figure 1.2)

Phraseological Units

<i>Nominations</i>	<i>Propositions</i>
<i>Idioms:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Pull someone's leg</i> - <i>Red herring</i> - <i>Shoot the breeze</i> - <i>Spill the beans</i> - <i>Red tape</i> - <i>Mare's nest</i> 	<i>Proverbs:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>One swallow does not make a summer</i>
	<i>Commonplaces:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>We live and learn</i>
	<i>Routine formulae:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Many happy returns</i>
	<i>Slogans:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Safety first!</i>
	<i>Commandments and maxims:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Thou shalt not kill</i>
<i>Non-Idioms:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Unconditional surrender</i> - <i>The Black sea</i> - <i>The Golden Twenties</i> - <i>Of paramount importance</i> - <i>Wet to the skin</i> - <i>Beyond compare</i> 	<i>Quotations and Winged words:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Where ignorance is bliss, 'tis folly to be wise</i> - <i>A Jekyll and Hyde</i>

(Figure 1.2)

In Karakalpak language, use of word combinations, word groups, phraseological units have developed by linguists, scientists, and real life situations in the many years that also give more important experiences about language phenomena. In spoken language we found one meaning word groups which means structural compositions includes two or more than words and give a one meaning or made from word compositions to identified one meaning. But this word groups

have separated other simple or complex sentences because, they made strong structures in one line. Moreover, they joined each other with their lexical characteristics, also loose fundamental characters in the sentence and give abstract meaning to the using conditions. In Karakalpak language , phraseological word combinations classified with following structure:

- 1) *Frazelohiyalıq birlik*
- 2) *Frazeologiyalıq o'tlesiw*
- 3) *Frazeologiyalıq dizbek* [5, p 8]

“Frazeologiyalıq o'tlesiwler” this type of word groups joined in the sentence according to lexical features and they prepared for users abstract meaning through the communicational situations and to attempt more emphasize and improve their impacts to the this word using condition. For instance,

“... so'zdin' qıyıwın kelistirip qamırdan qıl suwırg'anday so'ylegenine ta'n qaldı” (J.Aymurzaev)

“... iyshanlardın' so'zin tuń'lap salısı suwğa ketekendey húrresi uship otırdı (A.Begimov)

“Olar qızınıń aytqan so'zin kempirinen esitip tóbe shashı tikke turdı” (X.Seytov)

“ Dostıń ushin aqıldı sen tappasań, biziń qaygımız qayrılıp turıptı, dedi Miyrigu'l, al Allash bolsa , tuıyeden postın tastag'anday qılıp....” (M.Daribaev) [6,p 9]

In this example, phraseological word combinations have explained by it's lexical meaning, such as ,

- *qamırdan qıl suwırg'anday* – it means characterized that situations simply or ordinary, not damaged,
- *salısı suwğa ketiw* – this kind of situations give bad feelings,
- *húrresi ushıw-* frightening,

- *tóbe shashı tikke turıw – feel of unsatisfaction or scared situations,*
- *túyeden postın tastaǵanday – suddenly say about something*

“Frazeologiyalıq birlik” characterized that full of meaning in the sentences depending on their contextual meaning, in this reason phraseological word groups belong to their before and after word combinations and all word groups give emphatic meaning to the sentence. For example,

- *“ Óziniń aǵayini Juman Quljanovtı shalǵayınıń ushın jawıp, aman qorǵap, hesh qanday shara kórmesten qutqarıp jiberiwdi kózde tuttı” (J.Seytnazarov)*
- *“ Ol sózlerińdi qulaǵım shalıp tereń mánisin ańlamay qaldım” (A.Bekimbetov)*
- *“ Kóbirek jasaytuǵınıńa kóziń jete me ?” (X.seytov) [7, p11]*

In this examples, phraseological word groups *“ko’zde tuttı, qulag’im shalıp, jete me”* explained a meaning of full sentence and improved their impacts.

“Frazeologiyalıq dizbek” this type of phraseological word groups explained that they have different features above two types of phraseological word groups, and made from according to lexical meaning also create own general meaning to the context. For example,

- *“ Bul usınıstı hámme bir awızdan qabil aldı” (X.Seytov)*
- *“ Kelgenlerin hesh kimgе sezdirmeу, ne bilgeni ishinde bolip ornina barıp, qalay kelgen bolsa solay jattı” (J.Seytnazarov)*
- *“ Joldasları jaqqan ottı kórip quwanışı qoynına sıymaǵan Erpolat ásteǵana qosıq aytıp joldaslarına jetti” (M.Daribaev) [8, p 13]*

In this example, *“bir awızdan qabil alıw, ne bilgeni ishinde bolıw, quwanışı qoynına sıymaw”* phraseological word groups focus on stability of word compositions and based on full context.

This type of phraseological word groups close to the second type of phraseological phenomena with form of meaning and using forms.

Results and Discussion.

In the result we found that phraseological word combinations are essential tool of language communication. In our comparative and descriptive analysis showed that both target languages have differences and similarities when using idiomatic and set expressions, phraseological word combinations during the intentionally using form. Methods can be used during the investigation process, this following methods help to achieve our research results, linguistic analyses that provide important features of set expressions in linguistics, comparative analysis define the similarities and differences of set expressions in target languages. The Using of set expressions in English and Karakalpak languages have defined their important characteristics of both languages, it's linguo-stylistic features have a great role in linguistics. We suppose that analyzing and learning similarities and differences of both languages give suitable suggestions to the language learners and linguists during the linguistic course and speaking and writing systems.

Conclusion.

In linguistics, phraseology is the study of set or fixed expressions, such as idioms, phrasal verbs, and other types of multiword lexical units (often collectively referred to as phrasemes), in which the component parts of the expression take on a meaning more specific than, or otherwise not predictable from, the sum of their meanings when used independently. The basic units of analysis in phraseology are often referred to as phrasemes or phraseological units. Phraseological units are (according to Prof. Kunin A.V.) stable word-groups with partially or fully transferred meanings. According to Rosemarie Gläser, a phraseological unit is a lexicalized, reproducible billexemic or polylexemic word group in common use, which has relative syntactic and semantic stability, may be idiomatized, Phraseological units may carry connotations, and may have an emphatic or intensifying function in a text. [9] In conclusion, teaching and learning foreign

languages defined with their personal and impersonal characteristics that means depending on learners background knowledge about this language and how they understood way of learning process, learners intentions, and way of teaching foreign languages, it is also belong to teaching materials, strategies, methods, and teachers attitudes, also characterized with learning and teaching process should be highly motivated and encouraged during the process.

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